

Power Laws and the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

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A microcanonical distribution imposes an energy constraint (total E) on n particles. Probability of a particle having energy e is related to the rest of the particles sharing $E-e$. This seems to constitute a global constraint. In particular, one may derive a power law probability $P(e)$ proportional to $(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$ (1). If two particles have an energy which adds to e , then $(E-e)$ power $(n-3)$ should be the probability for any combination of two particles whose energies add to e . In other words, one has a global constraint. If $n \rightarrow$ infinite, however, then $n-2$ or $n-3$ tend to n . In such a case, one expects local equilibrium, so that the product $(E-e_1)$ power $(n-2)$ with $(E-e_2)$ power $(n-2)$ is equivalent to $(E-e_1-e_2)$ power $(n-3)$. This is equivalent to arguing that $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_1+e_2)$. In other words, one has local probabilities and properties and no longer the global one of the microcanonical distribution. This suggests that $(1 - e/(Bn))$ power (n) should tend to: d power (e/B) as $n \rightarrow$ infinite on physical grounds. (There should also be a math proof which exists in texts.) This is equivalent to the Maxwell-Boltzmann form $\exp(-e/T)$.

It may be noted that power laws appear for more cases than a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. For example, a n -vector with a fixed magnitude has a probability proportional to $P(e)dp = dp C (E-e)$ power $((n-3)/2)$ as shown in (2). The same arguments as above apply because for large n , the probabilities $P(e_1)$, $P(e_2)$ and $P(e_1+e_2)$ follow: $P(e_1)P(e_2)= P(e_1+e_2)$.

Microcanonical Power Law and Fixed Energy and Particle Number

In (1) it is argued that one may obtain a power law for n particles with a total energy of E i.e.

$P(e)$ is proportional to $(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$ ((1))

This is a global constraint because a particle having energy e means all of the rest of the particles must share the energy $E-e$. One may calculate:

$$P(e_1) = C (E-e_1) \text{ power } (n-2) \text{ ((2a))} \quad P(e_2) = C(E-e_2) \text{ power } (n-2) \text{ ((2b))}$$

$$P(e_1+e_2) = C^2 (E-e_1-e_2) \text{ power } (n-3) \text{ ((2c))}$$

A single particle with energy e_1+e_2 would have a probability: $C (E-e_1-e_2) \text{ power } (n-2) \text{ ((2d))}$

One may note that $E=e_1+e_2$, so n appears twice in the above expressions. One may factor out E so that one has the form: $E (1 - e/(Bn))$ power $(n-2)$ etc.

For a finite n , ((2a)) multiplied by ((2b)) does not equal ((2c)) and ((2c)) does not equal ((2d)). For n approaching infinite, however, using unnormalized expressions

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = (1 - e_1/(Bn) - e_2/(Bn) - e_1e_2/(BBnn)) \text{ power } (n-2) \text{ ((3a))}$$

And from ((2c)) $P(e_1+e_2) = (1-e_1/(Bn)-e_2/(Bn)) \text{ power } (n-2) * (1+(e_1+e_2)/(Bn)) \text{ power } (-1)$ ((3b))

Dividing ((3a)) by ((3b)) yields 1, i.e. a value independent of e_1, e_2 . Thus, unnormalized $P(e_1) * P(e_2) = \text{unnormalized } P(e_1+e_2)$ in the large n limit.

The same argument holds for dividing ((2c)) and ((2d)) in the large n limit.

As a result, the large n limit decouples the global dependence of probabilities and probabilities become independent, i.e.. $P(e_1+e_2)$ represents the unnormalized probability for one particle or for the product of two unnormalized probabilities $P(e_1) * P(e_2)$.

The form $P(e_1)P(e_2)= P(e_1+e_2)$ ((4)) has a formal solution of: $P(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$ ((4)) where T is a constant, i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann form. One may argue that any power law solution holds and that \exp is a special base value. In other words, different base values would be associated with different T values.

The above results also suggest that:

$(1+e/n) \text{ power}(n)$ with $n \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ becomes $\exp(e)$ where e is energy. ((5))

Although any base satisfies ((4)), only one base may satisfy ((5)) and this special base turns out to be \exp .

Decoupling and the Microcanonical Distribution

The above arguments were used for a gas of n particles with total energy E , but they apply to other cases of decoupling, i.e. a large n limit, breaking down the global restrictions of a power law. In particular, in (2) a formula is given which we argue applies to the probability of a component of an n vector $\{ p(i) \}$ with $i=1, n$ with a fixed magnitude E . In such a case, (2) states:

$$P(p(n)p(n)) dp(n) = dp(n) C (E- p(n)p(n)) \text{ power } ((n-3)/2) \quad ((6))$$

All of the arguments of the above section apply in the large n limit. In other words, the global restriction (i.e. power law form) becomes a local, independent probability type of argument which leads to an $\exp(-e/T)$ form of probability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine a microcanonical type of constraint for n particles (or a magnitude constraint for an n -vector) and note that it leads to a power law distribution (with different power expressions which are linear in n). We try to show that for large n , unnormalized probabilities decouple from the global restriction (microcanonical or fixed magnitude) so that one has the following relations: $P(e_1+e_2)$ one particle = $P(e_1+e_2)$ two particle = $P(e_1) P(e_2)$. In all cases, P is unnormalized here, i.e. is the function $\exp(-e/T)$ with T being a fixed constant.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution From a Microcanonical Power Law Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2023)
2. Lopez-Ruiz, R. and Calbet, Z. Why the Maxwell Distribution is the Attractive Fixed Point of the Boltzmann Equation 2006 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/nlin/0611044.pdf>